

Membrane potential based assay for SLC6A12 using HEK-293 SLC6A12 OE cells

PubChem ID: 1794822

Authors	Sara Tremolada ¹ , Loredana Redaelli ¹ , Lia Scarabottolo ¹
Affiliations	¹ Axxam S.p.A, Openzone Science Park, Bresso, Milan, Italy

Assay description

FLIPR[®] membrane potential dye measures changes of charges across the cell membrane, upon activation of SLC6A12. The assay allows the detection of ion channel and transporter modulation by increasing or decreasing the fluorescent signal as cellular membrane potential changes. When cells are depolarized dye enters the cells, causing an increase in fluorescent signal, conversely, cells hyperpolarization results in dye exit and decreased fluorescence (Figure 1).

SLC6A12 is a Na⁺ and Cl⁻ dependent GABA/betaine transporter that mediates an electrogenic transport with the stoichiometry of 3 Na⁺, 1 Cl⁻, 1 GABA/betaine.

As GABA transporter, it facilitates the termination of GABAergic signaling by transporting GABA together with sodium and chloride from the synaptic cleft into presynaptic neurons and surrounding glial cells; but it also plays an important role in osmoprotection of renal medullary cells as it facilitates the accumulation of the osmolyte betaine.

Figure 1. Principal of a FLIPR[®] membrane potential dye assay. The assay measures changes of charges across the cell membrane, consequence of channels and transporters modulation. The fluorescent signal increases in intensity during membrane depolarization as dye follows the positively charged ions inside the cell. During membrane hyperpolarization, fluorescent signal decreases in intensity as dye follows the positively charged ions out of the cell.

Assay protocol

HEK-293 JumpIN-SLC6A12 cells were subjected to pharmacological characterization.

Cell preparation

Cells were detached from 80-90% confluent flasks and seeded at 10'000 cells/well in black-clear bottom poly-D-Lysine coated 384 well plate in medium without the selective antibiotics and incubated 24 hours at 37°C, 5% CO₂. At the same time of seeding cells were induced with 1 µg/mL Doxycycline (not induced and mock control in parallel).

Membrane Potential assay

Medium was removed and cells were incubated 30 minutes at RT in 20 µL/well of FMP-Blue-Dye (0.5X dye dissolved in Standard Tyrode's Buffer as indicated in the manufacturer manual) and plates analysed at FLIPR^{TETRA} reader using a λexc 510 - 545nm / λem 565 - 625 nm filter.

To test pharmacology 20 µL/well of substrate GABA (2X in Standard Tyrode's buffer), starting from 5 mM, 1:5 dilution steps (8 concentrations, only buffer included) were online injected at the plate reader and fluorescence recorded.

Data analysis

FLIPR^{TETRA} measurements obtained from different well replicates were analysed by using the Screenworks software (Molecular Devices, Version 3.0.1.4). Absolute Response (RFU) is obtained applying "Subtract Bias on Sample: n" (where n = Timepoint of compound injection) whereas Assay Window Response (ΔF/F₀) is obtained applying "Response over Baseline" correction (where Baseline = Timepoint -1 and -2 before activator injection) and "Background Subtraction". Data were then exported as Area Under the Curve (AUC). Mean and standard deviation of each replicate were calculated on the exported data with Excel software, then values were used to create sigmoidal dose-response curves (variable slope) and to calculate EC₅₀/IC₅₀ values with GraphPad PRISM software (Version 6).

Additional information

Target data

SLC	SLC6A12
Synonyms	Sodium- And Chloride-Dependent Betaine Transporter, BGT-1
SLC sub-family	Solute Carrier Family 6 (Neurotransmitter Transporter)
UniProt ID	P48065
RESOLUTE Cell ID	CE06EC-1 (HEK-SLC6A12-WTOE-p5-6)

Assay data

	Compound name (1)	GABA
	PubChem CID	119
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma Aldrich, # A2129
	Mode of action	Substrate
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	EC ₅₀ = 36 μ M

Discussion

The Membrane Potential Assay for SLC6A12 showed a specific and dose-dependent fluorescent signal increase upon injection of GABA. The increase in the fluorescence intensity is a result of cell depolarization that reflects the co-transport of Na⁺ through the transporter together with the substrates.

Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).